

NEOLIBERALISM AND GLOBALIZATION - The Environment for the DEEP MAFIA for Plundering Peoples, Enslaving Peoples and Nations

Theory of Mafiotismus and "Financially Banking Resource-Based Technological Mafia-Driven Materialism" - The Real Ideology of the DEEP MAFIA

Does the Nobel Committee Serve the DEEP MAFIA in This Direction!?!?

Lord Prof. Momtchil Dobrev¹, Prof. Mariola Garibova- Dobreva²

^{1,2}Scientific Research Institute Dobrev & Halachev JSC.

ABSTRACT: Lord prof PhD PhD Momtchil Dobrev-Halachev developed 2010 "Financially banking resource-based technological mafia-driven materialism" as a based principle materialismus since more than 17 century.08 "Theory of generating of crises " , 2010 "Theory and praxice of the Mafiotismus" and 2001 " Theory of the mafia". Based on these two theories this paper explane the goals, purposes, principles and resultsof the neolibearalization and the process of globalization all over the world..

KEY WORDS: Neoliberalismus, Globalization, Mafiotismus, Crise, theory, finance.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the year 2010 Lord Prof. Momtchil Dobrev developed the "Theory of Mafiotismus" as a new state niveaou based on private and personal interests of the prime-minister, ministers, government. Based on this "Theory of Mafiotismus" Lord Prof. Momtchil Dobrev developed 2010 the "Financially banking resource-based technological mafia-driven materialism" as a based principle materialismus since more than 17 century.

In the year 2001 Lord Prof. Momtchil DObrevev developed the Theory of the mafia and Theory of corruption . All the both theories has been developed by analyzing of the mafia and the corruption all over the wprld. In Bulgaria, Germany, European Union, and other countires.

In the year 2008 Lord Prof. Momtchil Dobrev developed the "Theory of generating crises". The theory of generating crises has been developed by analyzing all the relationships between countries, and lysing the causes and consequences of crises. The theory examines all possible options for generating crises.

In this paper are described the conclusions of analysis of the neoliberalismus and the globalization under the principles of the Financial Banking Resource Technological Mafia – Driven Materialismus.

1.1 Introduce the Problem

The problemsand the negative results of the neoliberalizmus and the globalization all over the world are to be discussed. The truth of the principles and results of the neoliberalization and the globalization should be shown objeatively and under the real point of view undependant.

1.2. The covering of the real goals and results of liberzlication and the globalization - way how the world is working sinve the1970 and which power is driven it it very important of the covering the real process of neoliberalization and the globalization.

*1.4. The developed by Lord Prof. Dr. Momchil Dobrev **Financially banking resource-based technological mafia-driven materialism** cover the real urpose, golls, results of the neoliberalization and the globaloization.*

2. RESEARCH METHODS

Research methods of occurrence of Financially banking resource-based technological mafia-driven materialism and the MAFIOTISMUS, its logic of work, existence, management and its execution by activities by their representatives.

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Neo-liberalization analysis, programs, policies, processes, search and end result

Analysis of the advantages and disadvantages of neoliberalism

Analysis of the processes of globalization

Analysis of Hayek and Friedman's theories and other ideals of FBIHM Materialism

Analysis of the real outcomes for society of neoliberalism programs in Eastern Europe, Africa, Asia, and South America.

Analysis of capital movements and investments

Analysis of the real processes of obstruction of foreign investment

Analysis of the processes of morality and the unequal distribution in the programs of neoliberalism

3. PRINCIPLES OF THE GLOBAL MASONIC MAFIA ELITE - THE DEEP MAFIA - A BRIEF DESCRIPTION, CONCEPT, CONTENT, AND OF THE GLOBAL MASONIC ELITE

The global Masonic mafia elite - the deep mafia is a corporate, militarized, functionally defined, mafia group of people who manage and own financial, banking, corporate, IT companies, not elected by the citizens of the state, which actually govern not only a particular country but also group of countries, on the principles of Mafia and financial banking resource technological mafia Materialism.

The global Masonic mafia elite - the deep mafia has corrupted and mafiotized all spheres of society on which the government of a country, a union - in the case of the European Commission and the European Union, the United States, and other countries ruled by the people of the deep state.

All members of the global Masonic mafia elite - the deep mafia are Freemasons and belong to various secret societies, regardless of which. For years, all secret societies have been occupied from within by the representatives and bearers of the goals and aspirations of the Illuminati for a new world genocide and dictatorship over humanity. For these Freemasons the oath is to obey the law of the lodge and not to comply with any other laws - those of states, international law, unions and others and to do everything in the name and for the benefit of the lodge, observing only the laws of the lodge, but not to the state concerned, to international law, even to commit crimes, to help members of the lodge when they are in trouble, and to carry out the plan of the lodge. All laws and rules are subject to a vow of ideology and faith in Lucifer and the church of Lucifer / Satan.

And the plan is one - to conquer the world, to rule the world by one world government, only by them - the global Masonic mafia elite.

Concept - Prof. Momchil Dobrev

The Global Masonic Mafia Elite - THE DEEP MAFIA is an organization, structure, government, kleptocracy, and cryptocracy of a group of people from the financial banking, resource, technology, corporate elite. of the financial bank resource technological mafia materialized Materialism.

AREAS OF GOVERNANCE, CONTROL, OF THE GLOBAL MASONIC MAFIOTIZED ELITE - THE DEEP MAFIA AND MAFIOTISM

The global Masonic mafia elite - the deep mafia can be found in all spheres of public life, in all countries, governments.

The spheres of action, goals, tasks, management, control, manifestation of global Yamason mafia elite - the deep mafia and the global Masonic mafia elite through mafia and on the basis of financial banking resource technological mafia Materialism through the mafia are as follows:

-1 /. The sphere of state administration. This includes governments, prime ministers, ministers, government departments and institutions, local authorities and others, their control through compromising and other addictions, sexual addictions and other addictions.

-2 /. The sphere of politics-. This includes parliament, political parties, trade unions, movements, business and non-profit associations, the degradation of the political elite, their control through compromising, and other addictions, sexual addictions and other addictions.

-3 /. Control and management of national security systems, secret services, intelligence services. Control and management of the management and administration of intelligence services, intelligence agencies, internal security departments, intelligence services - space, central security services, national security services, intelligence and counterintelligence departments, intelligence departments of the Ministry of Defense, naval intelligence, air services, secret services, secret services

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4 /. Control and management of the sphere of military structures, defense structures, defense structures, military-industrial complex

5 /. The sphere of public services - healthcare, education, social assistance, etc.,

6 /. The sphere of the private sector, companies, corporations,

7 /. The sphere of the media / radio, television, newspapers, magazines and other media /, their control and management through racketeering, coercion, pressure, sanctions and others.

8 / The sphere of the "civil sector" / civil associations, non-governmental organizations and others /

9 /. Banking and financial sector

10 /. Social networks and information technologies

11 /. The sphere of the judicial system / judges, prosecutors, investigators /, their control through addictions -, bribes, gifts, excursions, knotrol through compromising, and other addictions - seucal, gambling and others.

12 /. The sphere of law enforcement institutions / prosecutor's office, investigation services, police /, their control through addictions, bribes, and others.

13 /. Control and management and conquest is the indebtedness of a country through the World Bank, through the International Monetary Fund, the European Central Bank, the International Bank for Settlements and other world banks.

14 /. Control and management of monopoly companies, controlling and having monopoly influence all over the world through investment companies, owned by the global Masonic mafia elite - BlackRock and other companies.

15 /. Leadership and intelligence management of the state treasury,

16. The overthrow of regimes through "yellow", "orange" revolutions and the appointment of governments, presidents to serve the interests of the deep state

17 /. Provoking occasions for starting and starting wars against countries whose territories with the respective natural resources are of interest to the representatives of the deep state.

18 /. Imposition of policy in relevant countries that are in the economic interests of the deep state and their profits from it.

19 /. Imposition of a policy in the case of NATO for the purpose of threats, wars against third countries from the territories of foreign countries.

20 /. Imposing a world government A new world order that will allow them to more easily govern countries, nations, peoples, economies, industries, finance, capital.

21 /. Creating conditions, causing chaos through various schemes and occasions - wars, refugee waves, crises - social, social, political, economic, state schemes with the ultimate goal of profits - economic, financial - profit and personal gain.

22 / - Management, control, manipulation, zombies of the civil society, through non-governmental organizations, their financing / example SOROS /,

23 /. Imposition of their requirements for military budgets of all countries in order to sell weapons from their companies in the military-industrial complex to countries, countries. 21 /. Control of criminal groups and groups

24 /. Control of trade, military, criminal groups, the defense industry, the financial sector, corporate media and counterterrorism.

25 /. Management of military budgets of states, at least more than half goes to military spending and the purchase of equipment and weapons.

26 /. Control and management of the military-industrial complex

27 / Control and management of the state money, budgets, of the respective state

28 /. Management of many non-governmental national and international structures - the Council on Foreign Relations, the Royal Institute of International Affairs, the Trust Commission, the Bilderberg Group, the Club of Rome, the Committee of 300,

29 /. Supranational governance of the countries of the planet.

30 /. Management of International Institutions - UN, UNICEF, World Health Organization,

31 /. Committing crimes against people, individuals, services

32 /. Imposing globalization as an ideology

33 /. Imposing the ideology and society of lesbianism, gay, bisexual and transgender people - LGBT people as a leader at the state level.

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- 34 /. Use of compromising control of individuals - politicians and any others on whom depends the state and other decisions responsible for society as a whole.
- 35 /. Create a program, plan, and accomplish the task of destroying Christianity.
- 36 / Destruction of the family as a basic building block of society.
- 37 /. Targeted organization of migration through waves of refugees, crises
- 38 /. Control and management of the election process in each state, imposing organization, management of the election process through various schemes of falsification and fraud.
- 39 /. Social terrorism of society from a moral, spiritual, economic point of view.
- 40 /. Total control of the population, by monitoring and controlling the permanent address, social activity on Facebook, Twitter, etc., driving licenses, watched or recorded movies, activity on various blogs, viewing or sending photos, detention by the police, subway trips, credit and debit cards, financial information, viewed photos, sent photos, face recognition by surveillance cameras, sent e-mails, received emails, search for information on the network, health card, education, train tickets, bus, plane, recorded applications in mobile phones, used applications, traffic, transactions online, etc.
- 41 /. Terrorist actions through the state, the United States and NATO, and other military organizations
 - 42 /. Terrorist actions through private formations
- 43 /. Ruin and collapse of the education system
- 44 /. killing the national achievements of democracy
- 45 /. destruction of the social system
- 46 /. polarization of society
- 47 /. destruction of national values
- 48 /. destruction of the national culture
- 49 /. destruction of rights and freedoms
- 50 /. destruction of the middle class
- 51 /. increasing poverty and inequality
- 52 /. increase begging
- 53 /. Indebtedness of countries, governments through the IMF, WB, ECB
- 54 /. Dependence of the media - television, radio, newspapers, magazines,
- 55 /. Control, management of the drug business since the 18th century by the black aristocracy
- 56 /. Creating inequalities in society, managing these inequalities, destroying the middle class, with the ultimate goal of enslaving society.
- 57 /. Creating conditions for control and management of the economies of entire countries with the sole purpose of personal gain.
- 58 /. Creation of a university elite - a Masonic mafia-dominated global elite to rule states, and other institutions in favor of the Global Masonic elite.
- 59 /. Control and management of education in a country in order to blunt, greater control and management of the masses and the younger generation in order to zombie and manage and control at any level - emotional, educational, social and others.
- 60 /. Creating a system for SOCIAL GEOCITE
- 61 /. Control is the management of health care with the ultimate goal of reducing the population of the planet,
- 62 /. Control and management of the system of drug development and dependence of the population on drugs.
- 63 /. Control and management of patents and developments and elimination of scientists who created discoveries that can improve people's lives.
- 64 /. Control and liquidate scientists, creators of drugs, but new methods of treatment that are cheap and hinder the wealth of the elite.
- 65 /. Control and liquidation of scientists creating systems for zero-point generators and free energy generators.
- 66 /. Control, management, drug production and addiction among the population with the ultimate goal of profit.
- 67. Control, creation of GMO products, food, for the purpose of profit and reduction of the population.
- 68 /. Population control and management through food, lethal medicine, lethal vaccines, psychiatric medicines, deadly food, deadly grain, deadly sweeteners, GMOs, deadly water, air,

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- 69 /. Control and management of the media, conquest of the media, and propaganda only of their goals, ideas, aspirations, plans, disguised under the slogan that care for humanity and the people in it.
- 70 /. Establish institutions that will govern countries, policies, such as the UN, UNICEF and others
 - 71 /. Control of the special and secret services through their Freemasons, to serve their lodges and personal interests, but not the laws of the respective state.
 - 72 /. Establishment of their own structures, in which their people will be members who will later govern and lead states - Council on Foreign Relations, 1921 and branches - Institute for Pacific Relations - New York, Center for Foreign Policy Studies - Paris, Institute for foreign policy - Hamburg, Royal Institute of International Affairs -1920, Bilberberg Group - 1954, Club of Rome - 1968, Trilateral Commission 1973, to determine the international policies of states, to govern states.
 - 73 /. Creation of an elite by the University of Global Masonic Mafia Elite - Yale University, Harvard, Columbia, Corel University, New York University, Sarah Lawrence College, Stanford University, University of Chicago, John Copkins, Brown University,
 - 74 /. Control and management of all Masonic lodges - Knights Templar, Freemasonry, Rosicrucians, lodge of Gnosticism, Kabbalism, the Illuminati Freemasons through the principles of the Church of Lucifer.
 - 75 /. Control and management of the elite and societies and states through Foundations - Rockefeller Foundation, Ford Foundation, Carnegie Endowment, Clinton Foundation,
 - 76 /. Media management and control,
 - proprietary television - BBC, CBC, CNN, CBS, ABC, CNN and others,
 - telegraph agencies - the Associated Press, Reuters and others,
 - newspapers - New York Times, Washington Post, Wall Street Journal, Boston Globe, Baltimore Sun, Chicago Sun Times, Los Angeles Stays, Houston Post, Minneapolis Star / Tribune and others,
 - magazines. Fortune, Time, Life, Money, People, Newsweek, Business Week, Readers Ridge, US EU News and World Report, and others, dozens of publishers,
 - 77 /. Propaganda and manipulation to reduce critical thinking
 - increasing the closedness, depression, dependence, feelings of slavery and dependence on the decisions and actions of the government
 - turning one's back on the real facts and evidence
 - dependence on propaganda
 - dependence on the propagated fear and stress
 - increase in mental illness
 - increase in drug abuse
 - increase in the number of homeless people
 - increase in the unemployed
 - increase in malnourished people
 - increase in malignant incurable diseases
 - increase in theft
 - increase in crime
 - increase in homicides
 - increasing the bankruptcies of companies
 - reducing the duration of
 - 78 /. Control by the global Yamason mafia elite of each state and its management through the control and management of the special services and secret services of the respective state.
 - 79 /. Control by the global Masonic mafia elite of all Masonic and other and all kinds of Masonic lodges around the world.
 - 80 /. Control and management of the election, election and appointment of presidents, prime ministers, chancellors in the respective countries from the structures of the deep mafia.
 - 81 /. Falsification of the elections in order to win the elections of this party, which is under the rule of global Masonic and mafia elite and the deep state. Managing the election fraud process in countries ruled by the global Masonic mafia elite and the deep mafia.

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82 /. The global Masonic mafia elite rules, controls the deep mafia in every country on the planet.

4. THE DEEP MAFIA AND THE SCIENCE OF THE ECONOMY

1 /. Funding of scientific teams of economists to impose economic theories and practices in favor of the deep mafia in order to guarantee their profits, enslavement of peoples, countries

2 /. Imposition of economic theories that will guarantee huge profits to the deep mafia.

3 /. Suppression of economic theories and developments that will reveal the essence of the deep mafia

4 /. Suppression of scientists who develop economic theories that contradict the interests and profits of the deep mafia.

5 /. Ignoring scientists who develop economic theories that run counter to the interests and profits of the deep mafia.

6 /. The refusal of such scientists to publish their scientific theories in world-renowned journals.

7 /. Restriction and control and management of publications in world-renowned scientific journals, websites, conferences.

8 /. Preventing the publication of articles and works and scientific theories and works of scientists that contradict the interests and pemalbs of the deep mafia.

9 /. Suppression in every way economically of the scientists developing economic theories that contradict the interests is the profits of the deep mafia.

10 /. Funding and material support for scientists who create scientific theories that benefit the deep mafia with millions of US dollars

11 /. Funding and material support for the publication of scientific journals that promote and proclaim scientific theories in favor of the deep mafia.

12 /. Funding and material support of NGOs by scientists, sociologists, political scientists, journalists, economists and others who promote and promote scientific theories that benefit the deep mafia.

13 /. Funding and material support of NGOs by scientists, sociologists, political scientists, journalists, economists, who will impose data that will benefit the scientific theories and practices of the deep mafia.

14 /. Financing and material support of media - magazines, newspapers, which will falsify data, trends, and will impose scientific theories and practices that are in favor of the deep mafia.

15 /. Creating strategies and tactics of data falsification, economic data, trends, forecasts, economic practices, management practices by media magazines, newspapers.

16 /. Financing and material support of media - TELEVISION CHANNELS, TELEVISIONS, INTERNET SITES, which will promote data, economic data, trends, forecasts, economic practices, management practices that are really false and support and are in favor of the goals.

17 /. Imposition of economic theories and practices and economic processes - such as globalization, liberalization, neo-liberalism, globo-fascism, in the governing practices of governments, economic unions.

18 /. Creating the relevant legislation that imposes the relevant processes, economic processes that are in favor of the deep mafia and its goals for global fascism and global governance.

19 /. Control and management of governments to pursue economic processes that benefit the deep mafia and its goals of global fascism and global governance.

20 /. Control and governance of governments to pursue financial schemes ostensibly to stimulate economic activity and solve global problems, and ultimately ensure the theft of financial resources from companies close to the deep mafia.

The deep mafia and its representatives act as a shadow government. The deep state does not respect the rights, freedoms, constitutions of the respective state, the treaties for the formation of unions, such as the European Union

In reality, the Deep State uses the following undemocratic models of governance as follows:

- Autocracy
- Oligarchy
- Plutocracy
- Kleptocracy
- Corporatocracy
- Cryptocracy

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All these systems of government are managed on the basis of the principles of MAFIOTISM and the Financial Bank Resource Technological Mafia Materialism.

5. DOES THE NOBEL COMMITTEE SERVE THE DEEP MAFIA IN THE ECONOMICS AWARDS?!?!

This is a question for readers, because above in the article we proved how the deep mafia creates inequalities and uses economic theories and practices for profit.

Below we quote the subjects for which the Nobel Prizes in Economics have been awarded, which complements the conclusion that science is being done in favor of the deep mafia and it is fully supported.

So the reader himself can answer the question:

Does the Nobel Committee serve the DEEP MAFIA in the distribution of Nobel Prizes in economics?!? !!

Here are the topics and developments for which the Nobel Prizes in Economics have been awarded

"for having developed and applied dynamic models for the analysis of economic processes"

"for the scientific work through which he has developed static and dynamic economic theory and actively contributed to raising the level of analysis in economic science"

"for his empirically founded interpretation of economic growth which has led to new and deepened insight into the economic and social structure and process of development"

"for their pioneering contributions to [general economic equilibrium theory](#) and welfare theory."

"for the development of the input-output method and for its application to important economic problems"

for their pioneering work in the [theory of money](#) and economic fluctuations and for their penetrating analysis of the interdependence of economic, social and institutional phenomena."

"for their contributions to the theory of [optimum allocation](#) of resources"

"for his achievements in the fields of [consumption](#) analysis, monetary history and theory and for his demonstration of the complexity of stabilisation policy"

"for their pathbreaking contribution to the theory of [international trade](#) and international [capital](#) movements"

for his pioneering research into the [decision-making](#) process within economic organizations"

"for their pioneering research into economic development research with particular consideration of the problems of [developing countries](#)."

"for the creation of [econometric](#) models and the application to the analysis of economic fluctuations and economic policies"

"for his analysis of [financial markets](#) and their relations to expenditure decisions, employment, production and prices"

"for his seminal studies of industrial structures, functioning of markets and causes and effects of [public regulation](#)"

„for having incorporated new analytical methods into economic theory and for his rigorous reformulation of the theory of [general equilibrium](#)"

"for having made fundamental contributions to the development of systems of [national accounts](#) and hence greatly improved the basis for empirical economic analysis"

"for his pioneering analyses of [saving](#) and of [financial markets](#)"

"for his development of the contractual and constitutional bases for the theory of economic and political [decision-making](#)"

"for his contributions to the theory of economic growth"

"for his pioneering contributions to the theory of markets and [efficient utilization of resources](#)"

"for his clarification of the probability theory foundations of [econometrics](#) and his analyses of simultaneous economic structures"

for their pioneering work in the theory of [financial economics](#)"

"for his discovery and clarification of the significance of [transaction costs](#) and [property rights](#) for the institutional structure and functioning of the economy"

"for having extended the domain of microeconomic analysis to a wide range of [human behaviour](#) and interaction, including non-market behaviour"

"for having renewed research in [economic history](#) by applying economic theory and quantitative methods in order to explain economic and institutional change"

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for their pioneering analysis of equilibria in the [theory of non-cooperative games](#)."

"for having developed and applied the hypothesis of [rational expectations](#), and thereby having transformed [macroeconomic analysis](#) and deepened our understanding of economic policy"

"for their fundamental contributions to the economic theory of incentives under asymmetric information"

"for a new method to determine the value of [derivatives](#)."

"for his [contributions](#) to [welfare economics](#)"

"for his analysis of [monetary](#) and [fiscal policy](#) under different [exchange rate](#) regimes and his analysis of optimum currency areas"

"for his development of theory and methods for analyzing selective samples"

"for his development of theory and methods for analyzing [discrete choice](#)"¹

"for their analyses of markets with [asymmetric information](#)"

"for having integrated insights from psychological research into economic science, especially concerning human judgment and decision-making under uncertainty"

"for having established laboratory experiments as a tool in empirical economic analysis, especially in the study of alternative market mechanisms"

"for methods of analyzing economic [time series](#) with time-varying [volatility \(ARCH\)](#)"

"for methods of analyzing economic time series with common trends ([cointegration](#))"

"for their contributions to dynamic macroeconomics: the time consistency of economic policy and the driving forces behind [business cycles](#)."

for having enhanced our understanding of conflict and cooperation through [game-theory](#) analysis."

"for his analysis of intertemporal tradeoffs in [macroeconomic](#) policy"

for having laid the foundations of [mechanism design](#) theory"

"for his analysis of trade patterns and location of economic activity"

"for her analysis of economic governance, especially the commons"

"for his analysis of economic governance, especially the boundaries of the firm"

"for their analysis of [markets with search frictions](#)"

"for their empirical research on cause and effect in the macroeconomy"

"for the theory of stable allocations and the /practice of market design."

"for their empirical analysis of asset prices."

"for his analysis of market power and regulation".

"for his analysis of consumption, poverty, and welfare".

6. PRINCIPLES of the Financially banking resource-based technological mafia-driven materialism of the DEEP MAFIA, The actions of George Soros based on the Prof. Momtchil DObev's "Financial Banking Resource-Technologically Mafia-Driven Materialismus"

6.1. The principles of the Financially banking resource-based technological mafia-driven materialism of the DEEP MAFIA

The only purpose is the profit and enslavement of peoples, states, governments, creation of monopolies.

Participating countries - banks, financial institutions, companies - oil, resources, steel, oil, food, medicines, fuels. Finance and money determine politics, wars, peace. Primary goal and approach: Central bank formation in the major countries to control not only finance, but also economic activity and politics. These central banks will be governed by governments, states, parties, citizens, a whole territory, in terms of money, investment, resources, use, in whose behalf and for what. These are the initial steps. Establishment of central banks in the major countries in fact to control not only finance but also economic activity. Establishment of central banks in countries owned by private individuals and private banks. This controls the economies of these countries, governments of these countries, citizens, over entire societies. Where central private banks are not allowed to be created in the countries - it is the occasion to generate civil wars, wars between states, trigger "revolutions" - to finance them from the bank-financial resources technological capital. Creating conditions for destabilization of the country concerned, importing corruption, provoking a civil war, provoking war, creating conditions for the maturing of an economic crisis, leading to the destabilization of the political power in the country. Generating and provoking wars, conflicts, fickle confessions, financing both the warring parties with loans - with the ultimate goal of profit, debt, then giving credit for the recovery of these states,

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lending to rebuild the economies of the warring states, shunning companies managing resources - oil, gold, trade, medicines, food, creating a military situation - unlocking - an institutional occasion. System: Funding both sides to wage war between them. Practical parties are indebted to banks, then banks and financial institutions finance the recovery of their economies. Profits are enormous. The profit rate for weapons and ammunition is the highest and most rapidly recoverable and revamped. They finance supplies of weapons, ammunition, food, clothing, ammunition, extra equipment, they actually manage the war process - when there is an advantage for one side, for the other. Realistically with supplies of weapons, ammunition, they manage the process of war - which side takes precedence and when and for how long.

The Goal:

Government control - not only through finances, but also by building up faithful government and state subjects - from universities, world institutions, clubs, lodges, foundations, which then either become presidents, prime ministers, ministers, leaders and important institutions .

Control of security services and control of compromise.

Control of whole countries

Through debt securities control of governments, states.

Money control, their circulation, movement, direction, direction.

Policy control and policies

Press control

Policy control

Control of the Masonic lodges

Purpose and purpose of war, military conflict, aggression - profit.

Control and avoid the introduction of technology.

Control and prevent the production of technology and free energy to be enjoyed by all people and peoples.

Control of patents that contribute to the development of civilization, not to see the world, to be forgotten, not to be used.

Control and liquidation of scientists who have created innovative solutions for the benefit of humanity in science, technology, and treatment.

Control and avoidance of the production of treatments for the treatment of lethal diseases.

Import and export of corruption in one country to its destabilization.

Imports of terrorism.

Export and import of mafia principles in one country

Debt economy, money control. A person who controls money controls states, societies, peoples, governments.

Manifestation of the masses, peoples, personalities.

Personality control, with debit, credit cards, mobile phones, mobile applications - uninterrupted control.

Civil Society Control through Foundations - NGOs to Replace Public Opinion, Funding to Control and Manage Society.

Command not all resources of the earth, oil, gold, silver, uranium and income from them.

Managing the population through illnesses.

Management of the population through pollution of the environment

Technology management, when technology is being introduced into a conversion, why not, keep another, disappear.

Private repositories of tremendous wealth.

Crisis Generation - Any, Economic, Currency, Social, Refugee, Conflict, War Political Crisis ,. The financial crisis occurs the fastest, the currency crisis occurs instantly, They are followed by economic crises, Part of the financial crisis and one kind of it is the currency crisis. There is a financial crisis. There are always economic crises.

World currency controlled by members.

Destabilization - chaos of one country, a whole system, inside - without war, Destabilization - chaos in economic direction, Destabilizers - a chaos of society, Destabilization - a chaos of civil society, Destabilization of the currency, The destabilization of the economy, Destabilization - anxiety in education

Breaking the moral norms of a society, Breaking the ethical norms of a society

Crisis management - with the ultimate goal of profit - speculative profit.

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Destabilization - of a society at all levels using - ethnicity, religion

All this without WAR

Governing a country, whole countries, - in the case of the European Union, with the ultimate goal of profit -

Managing a state at all levels through its close and faithful people

Demoralizing one community

Replace civil society with its structures to replace the real Citizenship

Financing and support of media - television, newspapers, magazines, etc., Financing political parties for the purpose of getting power and using them, Financing of individuals who will be useful in the future for its purposes - social scientists, political scientists, politicians, scientists, historians, of all classes.

Crisis generation schemes:

- Invocation of wars
- Invocation of military conflicts
- Call for military intervention in a country
- Import and export of corruption, mafia,
 - Tracking money out of circulation, it immediately creates economic crises. In turn, they cause huge damage to whole countries. Accordingly, he gets loans.
- Crisis crisis - caused - creates economic, social, demographic, social, political crises.
- Inviting the Financial Crisis
- Inviting the Currency Crisis
- Inviting Economic Crises
- The call for an otic crisis - not always last
- Increase of deficit - for the purpose of signing
- World wars become redundant due to the danger of nuclear exchange, so terrorism will be used.
- Managing the population through fear. Planting fear among the population.
- Creating an antipode - through fear, manipulation, Creating an intrigue machine, Creating a machine for seeming occasions
 - for wars, conflicts, aggressions, diversions,,Induction of inflation and deflation afterwards,Creating antipodes - with the ultimate goal of the Cold War battle - generates huge profits, enormous cash flows,
 - Possession of resources
 - The machine of intrigue and compromise and the creation of fake occasions.
 - Generating, financing and combating terrorism.

Crisis generation schemes:

- Privacy of chaos in one country - political, economic.
- Import and export of corruption, mafia,
 - Tracking money out of circulation, it immediately creates economic crises. In turn, they cause huge damage to whole countries. Accordingly, he gets loans.
- Crisis crisis - caused - creates economic, social, demographic, social, political crises.
- Inviting the Financial Crisis,-Inviting the Currency Crisis, -Inviting Economic Crises
- The call for an otic crisis - not always last
- Increase of deficit - for the purpose of signing
- World wars become redundant due to the danger of nuclear exchange, so we will use the creation of the HHS in whole countries.
 - Creating an intrigue machine, Creating a machine for seeming occasions - for wars, conflicts, aggressions, diversions,
 - Induction of inflation and deflation afterwards
 - - Not the resources
 - The machine of intrigue and compromise and the creation of fake occasions.
 - Generating, financing and combating terrorism, Generating the WAVE WAVE and the profit from it.

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- Generation of "DEMOCRATIC REVOLUTION" - YELLOW REVOLUTION and others in different sidelines - and use of chaos to penetrate certain companies to STILL COUNTRY MATERIALS - the example of Libya and other countries.

6.2/ PRINCIPLES of creating the EUROPEAN UNION of the MAFIOTISMUS and the DEEP MAFIA and of the financial bank resource technological mafia – driven materialism based on the Neoliberalism and Globalization

THE EUROPEAN UNION IS A PROJECT OF THE REPRESENTATIVES OF THE "FINANCIAL - BANK RESOURCE TECHNOLOGY MAFIA-DRIVEN MATERIALISM".

OBJECTIVES FOR THE ESTABLISHMENT OF THE EUROPEAN UNION

Controlling and managing all the countries of Europe through an organization

Establishment and control and management of an organization that is supranational, according to which decisions all countries should comply.

Introducing a single currency for Europe

Consumption control and management across Europe

Market control and management in Europe

Controlling and managing consumer markets and maximizing profits in Europe

Controlling and managing nations, peoples, consumption in Europe

Controlling and managing income distribution in Europe

Investment Control and Management in Europe

Controlling and managing the movement of money in Europe

Controlling and managing the banking and financial system across Europe through one institution - the European Central Bank.

Controlling and managing consumer markets and maximizing profits in Europe

Controlling and Managing Industries in Europe

Control and management of industrial production in Europe

Control and Management of All Industries in Europe

Control and management of health systems in Europe

Controlling and managing education in Europe

Controlling and managing pharmaceuticals and maximizing profits in Europe

Control and management of the demographic process

Control and management of immigration processes in Europe

Principles of operation creation and control and management of the EUROPEAN UNION

Establishing an alliance of states with the ultimate goal of being able to manage more easily from one place, from one governing body, to control, to make dependent financial, market, investment, production, military, resource, industrial, with the ultimate goal profits at any level.

Extending and creating markets for their products, in particular to Germany. France,. After all, profits return to Germany, France, Italy, the Netherlands.

Expanding and creating markets for their food producers from Germany France, Italy,

Create double standards for food sold in Germany and another standard sold in Bulgaria.

Expanding markets for sale to their producers of meat, cheese, pastries, all kinds of products.

Create markets for selling their tools for home use as well as for German business specialists

Creating conditions for foreign investments - real money laundering, export of income, export of products, making profits outside the country where the investment is made. The cheap labor is actually used, in the country where it is put to expansion, no profit is made in this country, no taxes are paid, the profits go to the parent companies in Germany, France, USA and others. Establishing conditions for the entry of their chains for the sale of food and other goods in the countries that have been admitted to EU expansion, money laundering, sale of goods, services of the countries of the mother companies mainly from Germany, France and others, hiding profits, exporting profits on criminal roads.

. Establishing conditions for export of national income - without being taxed, and others.

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Establishing conditions for depopulation of the country concerned.

Creating of conditions for islamization

Creating chaos conditions in the respective country.

Establishing terms of intermediate acquisition of financing from the European funds - between 30% and 40%.

Establishing terms and conditions those companies to participate in infrastructure projects and projects.

Establishing conditionsa that, when financing, the respective companies in the respective country should be obliged to buy equipment, equipments, machines, equipment, goals, installations, goals, production lines in Germany, France.

Establishinh conditions of dependence of the banking system of the respective country from the respective banks of MAFIA. And of FINANCIAL-BANK RESOURCE - TECHNOLOGICAL MATERIALISM. The Banking Institutions of Europe - Germany, Italy, France - USA - of the Rothschild Rockefellers Creating a Common Military Block - Creating the North Atlantic Treaty - NATO April 4, 1949 in Brussels and thus security control and dependence of all US states, the US military complex of the United States, the establishment of US bases in the countries of the Union of Germany.

7. FORMULA OF THE MAFIOTISMUS of THE DEEP MAFIA

The most simple model of the mafiotismus that describes the factors that affect the amount, type, and etc of the mafia is the following:

MAFIOTISMUS = PERSONAL Power / on the top of Europa state institutions /EU. EC, European courts, European Parliament / state and etc./ + Influence + Connections / to personal, private companies + Interests / personal, private, corporative / + ORDER / ORDERS + Personal management of all state neveaus + Personal Control of all states niveausMafia structure / inside or outside / + Monopolity Riegths + laws / rules / practices / procedures + possibility of taking an alternative decision - obligation - responsibilities - morality / ethics + Personal management and personal control of distribution of public state monetary and other resource (including European funds and funds).

This MAFIOTISMUS ia a base of the “ Financially banking resource-based technological mafia-driven Materialism “ developed by Lod Prof. Prof. Prof. Momtchil Dobrev – Halachev e той e в основата на Европейския Съюз , Европейската комисия и всички европейски институции.

8. NEOLIBERALISM AND GLOBALIZATION - The environment for generating crises and conquering entire peoples, markets, industries from international corporations, financial institutions, oligarchy, representatives of THE DEEP MAFIA

Neoliberalism around the world leads to globalization of the global economy. There is a cyclical nature of production and crises persist. Crises are becoming more common. Crises are increasingly difficult to overcome

Progressive technologies are evolving and there is a strategic superiority of certain countries over the rest of the world.

Globalization has led to the full exploitation of small nations by large nations. Neoliberalazilm and globalization of the south bring peoples closer, but in reality they move them away, and the real enslavement of one country to another is cured. They bring the countries close to development, which makes the crisis immediately affect all other countries in this industrial and other development. Smaller countries are dragged down by lag and to a lesser extent.

The countries of the world are not on a par with industrial and spiritual and cultural development.

In neoliberalism, the global and internal markets are a major driver of economic development.

Different countries have different levels of economic development. the corresponding varying degrees of competitiveness.

The economies of developed countries produce cheaper, produce more and more qualitatively, thus imposing their production and thus conquering the markets of smaller, less developed countries. It is a process of doomed poverty.

Neoliberalism elevates in a natural way, using the political system and political parties to impose a financial oligarchy. The financial oligarchy governs governments and states respectively.

In turn, the intersection of financial interests and politics gives birth not only to the financial oligarchy but also to corruption and the mafia in the state at all levels.

The financial oligarchy, large corporations also hold elite government in the state.

In neo-liberalism, there can be no real civil society and theft to control the government.

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Governments actually create laws that can stretch certain corporate interests, support their business activities, enforce and legitimize corrupt practices, enforce laws that exclude real civil society, enforce laws that legitimize the mafia in governments, and the financial mafia.

In reality, governments create and enact laws that legitimize theft, corruption, mafia, and work in the country.

The media is conquered by certain corporations that govern governments and the state.

The media really cannot fulfill its function.

Actually, the manipulation in favor of the financial and oligarchic mafia is carried out by the media, which do not allow other thinking, opinion, impose the obedience to the mafia as a way of jamming, governing, organization of society.

The media is highly dependent on the oligarchs and the oligarchic mafia.

The oligarchic mafia rules governments, and thus entire countries.

THE PURPOSE IS GLOBALIZATION TO BECOME CONTROLLED - which the oligarchic mafia will not allow.

In reality, there is no specialization of a particular country to be competitive in other countries.

GLOBALIZATION SPECIALIZED AND CONTROLLED

The consumer society is only in the interest and is profitable only for developed countries.

In this way, they sell their goods and services in the respective countries for a long period of time.

NEOLIBERALISM - IMPOSED IN EUROPE - IS LEADING TO GLOBALIZATION OF THE GLOBAL ECONOMY.

THE CYCLICAL NATURE OF PRODUCTION AND CRISES PERSISTS.

CRISES ARE BECOMING MORE COMMON. CRISES ARE INCREASINGLY DIFFICULT TO OVERCOME

PROGRESSIVE TECHNOLOGIES ARE EVOLVING, STRATEGICALLY SUPERIOR TO THE REST OF THE WORLD.

GLOBALIZATION HAS LED TO THE FULL EXPLOITATION OF SMALL NATIONS BY LARGE NATIONS.

NEOLIBERALISM AND GLOBALIZATION ARE BRINGING PEOPLES CLOSER.

THEY BRING THE COUNTRIES CLOSE TO DEVELOPMENT, WHICH MAKES THE CRISIS IMMEDIATELY AFFECT ALL OTHER COUNTRIES IN THIS INDUSTRIAL AND OTHER DEVELOPMENT.

IN SMALLER COUNTRIES, THE ATTRACTION IS SLOW LAG AND TO A LESSER EXTENT.

THE NATIONS OF THE PEOPLE ARE NOT ON A PAR WITH INDUSTRIAL AND SPIRITUAL AND CULTURAL DEVELOPMENT,

IN GREECE, THERE ARE ALL THE BASIC FEATURES OF NEOLIBERALISM - NAMELY, THAT THE GOVERNMENT DOES NOT INTERFERE WITH THE ECONOMY AT ALL, IE. IT HAS LEFT THE MARKET ALONE TO DETERMINE THE RULES AND, ON THE OTHER HAND, THERE IS A HIGH-COST SOCIAL SYSTEM - IN THE FIELD OF PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION IN HEALTH.

ALL GREEK GOVERNMENTS KNEW THAT IN ONE LANGUAGE THE COUNTRY WOULD NOT BE ABLE TO SERVICE ITS DEBTS

IN NEOLIBERALISM, THE GLOBAL AND INTERNAL MARKETS ARE A MAJOR DRIVER OF ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT.

DIFFERENT COUNTRIES HAVE DIFFERENT LEVELS OF ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT. THE CORRESPONDING VARYING DEGREES OF COMPETITIVENESS. P.

THE ECONOMIES OF DEVELOPED COUNTRIES PRODUCE CHEAPER, PRODUCE MORE AND MORE QUALITATIVELY, THUS IMPOSING THEIR PRODUCTION AND THUS CONQUERING THE MARKETS OF SMALLER, LESS DEVELOPED COUNTRIES.

IT IS A PROCESS OF DOOMED POVERTY.

NEOLIBERALISM ELEVATES IN A NATURAL WAY, USING THE POLITICAL SYSTEM AND POLITICAL PARTIES TO IMPOSE A FINANCIAL OLIGARCHY.

THE GREEK BANKING SYSTEM FOCUSES MORE ON THE MEANS OF PRODUCTION IN GREECE.

THE FINANCIAL OLIGARCHY IS GOVERNED BY THE GOVERNMENT AND THE STATE RESPECTIVELY.

IN TURN, THE INTERSECTION OF FINANCIAL INTERESTS AND POLITICS GIVES BIRTH NOT ONLY TO THE FINANCIAL OLIGARCHY BUT ALSO TO CORRUPTION AND THE MAFIA IN THE STATE AT ALL LEVELS.

THE FINANCIAL OLIGARCHY, THE LARGE CORPORATIONS, HOLD AND THUS GOVERN THE GOVERNMENT IN THE ELITE STATE.

IN NEO-LIBERALISM, THERE CAN BE NO REAL CIVIL SOCIETY AND THEFT TO CONTROL THE GOVERNMENT.

IN REALITY, GOVERNMENTS CREATE LAWS THAT CAN ADVANCE CERTAIN CORPORATE INTERESTS AND SUPPORT SUCH ACTIVITIES.

IN REALITY, GOVERNMENTS CREATE AND ENACT LAWS THAT LEGITIMIZE THEFT, CORRUPTION, MAFIA, AND WORK IN THE COUNTRY.

THE MEDIA IS CONQUERED BY CERTAIN CORPORATIONS THAT GOVERN GOVERNMENTS AND THE STATE.

THE MEDIA REALLY CANNOT PERFORM ITS FUNCTION.

ACTUALLY, THE MANIPULATION IN FAVOR OF THE FINANCIAL AND OLIGARCHIC MAFIA IS CARRIED OUT BY THE MEDIA, WHICH DO NOT ALLOW OTHER THINKING, OPINION, IMPOSE THE OBEDIENCE TO THE MAFIA AS A WAY OF JAMMING, GOVERNING, ORGANIZATION OF SOCIETY.

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THE MEDIA IS HIGHLY DEPENDENT ON THE OLIGARCHS AND THE OLIGARCHIC MAFIA.

THE OLIGARCHIC MAFIA RULES GOVERNMENTS, AND THUS ENTIRE COUNTRIES.

GLOBALIZATION SPECIALIZED AND CONTROLLED

THE CONSUMER SOCIETY IS INTERESTS AND IS FAVORABLE FOR DEVELOPED COUNTRIES.

WHY THEY ARE PLACING THE GOODS IN THE RELEVANT COUNTRIES AND FOR A LONG TIME.

NEOLIBERALISM SEES COMPETITION AS A DEFINITIVE CHARACTERISTICS OF ALL HUMAN RELATIONS.

INEQUALITY IS ELEVATED AS VALUE, MORALITY, QUALITY OF SOCIETY.

THE MARKET IS THAT THE GUARANTEE THAT EVERYONE MAKES WHAT IT DESERVES.

NEOLIBERALISM REFINES CITIZENS ONLY AS CONSUMERS WHOSE CHOICE IS BY BUYING AND SELLING.

THIS IS THE PROCESS OF REWARDING QUALITY AND PURSUING THE INEFFICIENCY OF THE MARKET THAT PROVIDES BENEFITS TO ALL HUMAN RELATIONS.

NEOLIBERALISM IS BASED ON:

THE 2008 FINANCIAL COLLAPSE, THE WEALTH RELEASE, THE POWER OF MANAGING AND PARTICIPATING IN THE MAFIA, THE COLLAPSE IN EDUCATION AND HEALTH WILL INCREASE TOWARDS

UNDER NEOLIBERALISM, RESTRICTING COMPETITION IS A VIEW OF FREEDOM. UNDER NEOLIBERALISM, TAXES AND REGULATIONS SHOULD BE MINORIZED, ALL PUBLIC SERVICES AND PUBLIC CONSUMPTION SHOULD BE PROVIDED.

EVERY REPRESENTATIVE OF THE WORKERS IN CONCLUSION OF COLLECTIVE LABOR CONTRACTS IS BY THEIR DISTORTION OF THE MARKET.

INEQUALITY IS RISE AS A VALUE, MORAL.

INEQUALITY IS A GENERATOR OF WEALTH THAT "ENRICHES" FROM THE HIGHEST LEVELS OF WEALTH TO THE LOWEST LEVELS OF POVERTY.

ALL CONDITIONS FOR CREATING A LEVEL SOCIETY UNDER NEOLIBERALISM HUMAN THE MORALITY AND THE MORAL AND ETHICAL VALUES OF HUMAN.

THE MARKET IS THE ONE THAT GUARANTEES THAT EVERYONE WILL RECEIVE WHAT IT DESERVES.

REALLY STRUCTURAL UNEMPLOYMENT MEANS THAT THAT SOMEONE DOES NOT WORK MEAN THAT IT IS NOT ENTERPRISE.

NO MATTER UNAFFORDABLE HOUSING COSTS, INCREASING THOSE OF HOUSING, INCREASING PARTITIONS AND BARRIERS TO EDUCATION, ZDRAVEOPOZVANE, NEVER MIND CONSTANTLY INCREASING PRICES, COSTS, DEBT SPIRAL WITH INCREASING CONSUMER CONSUMER PRICES FOR SERVICES.

IT DOESN'T MEAN THAT CHILDREN DO NOT HAVE EQUAL ACCESS TO EDUCATION AND HEALTH - THE PARENTS ARE TO BLAME.

AS THE FLAGSHIP OF ALL LIFE, THE WORD "COMPETITION" IS THE ONE THAT REGULATES ALL HUMAN RELATIONS IN ALL DIRECTIONS AND AREAS.

THE NEOLIBERASIM IS BORN 1938. IN PARIS, ATTENDED BY TWO PEOPLE LUDWIG VON MISES AND FRIEDRICH HAYEK - FROM AUSTRIA

THE TWO DEFINITES SOCIALDEMOCRACY AS A MANIFESTATION OF COLLECTIVISM THAT INHABITS THE SAME SPECTRUM AS NAZISM AND COMMUNISM. "

ACCORDING TO HAYEK IN "THE ROAD TO SLAVERY" SINCE 1944. EVERY GOVERNMENTAL PLANNING THAT SMASHES INDIVIDUALISM LEADS TO TOTYLARY CONTROL. AND MOSES FINDS THIS IN HIS BUREAUCRACY.

THEY ARE RICH SPONSORS MOVEMENT FORMED BY HAYEK - SOCIETY "MES CLOAK" WHO SUPPORTS THIS IDEOALOGOIYA - - AMERICAN PREDPRIAMECHISKI INSTITUTE, FOUNDATION "HERITAGE" INSTITUTE "KATE" INSTITUTE FOR ECONOMIC MATTERS, CENTER FOR POLICY RESEARCH AND INSTUTAT "ADAM SMIT4.

UNDER HAЕК, GOVERNMENTS MUST REGULATE COMPETITION, DON'T MONOPOLES FORM, AND MULTIPLE FRIDMANT INVOLVES THROUGH MONOTOPHED

AFTER AFTER WWII WILL APPLY JOHN MAINARD KANES'S ECONOMIC MODEL, WHICH OFFERED LOWER EMPLOYMENT, AND LOVE, HIGH DUES, PULLUMS, PULLUMS, AND PULLUMS

IN THE 1970s, KEYNES' POLICIES BEGAN TO SKID, AND AS FRIEDMAN'S "IWE" MONETARY SYSTEM. THESE MONETARY POLICY IS PERCEIVED BY JIMMY CARTER IN THE USA AND JIVA CALLAHAN BY VELIKOBRIANITSYA, AND BY MARGARET THATCHER AND RONALD REAGAN IN THE US MAKE MASSIVE TAX INCENTIVES CLINICAL TRIALS FOR RICH, LUBRICANTS AND TRADE UNIONS, DEREGULATION, PRIVATIZATION, COMPETITION IN PUBLIC SERVICES.

AT THIS TIME, THIS POLICY WAS ENFORCED AND ENFORCED BY THE IMF, THE WORLD BANK, THE WORLD TRADE ORGANIZATION.

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THIS IS A LIBERAL DICTATION.

DEPRIVATION OF THE ROLE OF TRADE UNIONS AND THE COLLECTIVE BARGAINING OF WAGES REDUCE THE LEVEL OF WAGES.

FREEDOM FROM REGULATION LEAD TO:

- HIGH INTEREST RATING,
- LAWS ON FINANCIAL INSTITUTIONS
- UNDER NEOLIBERALISM, FREEDOM OF TAXES MEANS FREEDOM FROM THE DISTRIBUTION OF PUBLIC GOODS. NEOLIBERAL THEORITICS ARE PROTECTING THE USE OF CRISIS.
- WHEN NEOLIBERAL POLICY CANNOT BE IMPLEMENTED AT THE LOCAL LEVEL, IT IS IMPOSED INTERNATIONAL, BY TRADE AGREEMENTS.

DISPUTE RESOLUTION MECHANISM INCLUDING "DISPUTE MECHANISM FOR INTER-INVESTORS AND STATES".

EVERYDAY EVERYDAY ALL STATE GOVERNMENTS ALL STATES, STATES, STATES, STATES, STATES, STATES, STATES AND STATES REALLY DEMOCRACY IS REDUCED ONLY AS A "CONCEPT WITHOUT REAL CONTENT.

UNDER NEOLIBERALISM UNIVERSAL COMPETITION IS NECESSARY.

INEQUALITIES IN DISTRIBUTION AND INCOME AND WEALTH HAVE PLUMMETED AFTER 60 YEARS.

LUBRICATION OF TRADE UNIONS, INCREASING TAXES, RENTS, INTEREST, LOANS, DEBT PRIVATIZATION AND DEGRULATION ARE POLICIES OF NEOLIBERALISM.

PRIVATIZATION OF PUBLIC SERVICES SUCH AS ELECTRICITY, OTOPLENEIE, WATER, ZDRAVEOPOZVANE, EDUCATION, ROADS, TRAINS, PLACE CORPORATIONS TO SET ITSELF PRICES AS YOU WANT WITHOUT ANY REULATSIYA AND ECONOMIC JUSTIFICATION AND THE PRACTICAL ENABLES IMMENSE PROFITS AND LEGALIZED RACKETEERING AND COERCION PAYING ANYTHING OWNED BY CITIZENS.

AND DESPITE THE HIGH PRICES, THE CITIZENS HAVE NO CHOICE, THEY HAVE NO CHOICE, THEY ARE MADE TO PAY THE REQUIRED PRICES AND VALUE.

THESE WHOSE CONCESSION MANAGEMENT AND PRIVATIZED SERVICES MANAGER INCREASE PROPERTY.

REAL INTEREST IS REAL PROFITABLE UNPRODUCTIVE INCOME. THE RICH ARE GAINING MORE CONTROL OVER MONEY. THE STATE IS LOADING LOANS TO CITIZENS.

REALLY THE TRANSFER IS ONLY IN ONE SINGLE DIRECTION - FROM PEOPLE WHO MAKE MONEY FROM CREATING NEW GOODS OR SERVICES TO THE SERVICES OF THESE POVITS AND FAVORITES

EARNED EARNINGS REALLY PAY THE UNDERTAIN UNDERTAIN INCOME.

AND FROM OTHER PARTIES IF THE BANKS ARE BALANCING, THE STATE HELPS THEM TO COME OUT OF THE CURRENT CRISIS

REALLY LIVING SERVICES MAY NOT BE ALLOWED TO BANK.

COMPETITION REALLY CAN'T MAKE THIS TASK.

RISK STAYS IN THE STATE.

GOVERNMENTS ARE IMPROVED. PUBLIC SERVICES ARE DIRECTED, CORPORATIONS DEGREE AND REGULATED ONLY BY CITIZENS.

REALLY THAT THE MAFITISM OF PROF. MOMBIL GOODWOOD, WHICH GOVERNMENTS LOSED MORAL POWER, MORAL ASSESSMENT OF CITIZENS, REALLY AVAILABLE ONE OF THE TOTALITARITISM OR MAFIOTISMUS.

THE INVISIBLE HAND DOCTRINE IS REALLY NOT INVISIBLE, BUT IT IS EXACTLY GOOD BY Mafia MANAGEMENT IN THE STATE, GOVERNMENT, COMPANIES.

NEOLIBERALISM IS A REAL FAILURE.

In reality, the market is managed by the Mafia, prices, values are managed by the Mafia, international corporations and the oligarchy.

THE MARKET WANTS WHAT THEY REALLY WANT AS THE PRICE, THE VALUE OF THE CORPORATIONS.

NEOLIBERALISM IS NOT ANONYMOUS.

THE REALLY IDEOLOGIES OF Hayek, Mises, and Friedman are ideologues of the mafioticism of financial-banking recourse technology.

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9. THROUGH NEOLIBERALISM AND GLOBALIZATION, THE REPRESENTATIVES OF FBMM MATERIALISM ARE MANAGING AND CREATING INEQUALITIES THROUGHOUT THE WORLD OF THE DEEP MAFIA

Through Neoliberalism and Globalization REPRESENTATIVES OF FINANCIAL BANKING RESOURCES TECHNICAL MAPHOTIZED MATERIALISM. They manage the creation of inequalities, conquer markets, consumption in entire countries, monopolize production, monopolize trade and monopolize consumption and sales of goods and services.

Creating and managing inequality through:

- Through trade wars
- Through sanctions
- Through international financial institutions - IMF, World Bank, World Trade Organization.
- Through laws, insurance, regulations, benefits, pensions
- Through the pension system
- Through education
- Through healthcare - hospital, health insurance, in-patient and out-of-hospital care, establishment of corrupt practices in hospitals, polyclinics, medical guilds, lack of treatment, no access to treatment, no access to medicines
- Through pharmaceuticals - creating drugs that cause addiction, morbidity,
- through the banking system
- through the financial system
- by generating currency, economic, governmental,
- through the economy
- through the media
- through psychoses, psycho-attacks
- through businesses for the poor
- by increasing rental properties in entire cities, entire countries
- through lawlessness in the judicial system
- through lack of justice, legality in the judicial system
- by mafiaing the judiciary
- through the mafia of the administrations - state, municipal
- by mobbing the executive - the Council of Ministers, the Ministries,
- by mafia of controlling and controlling institutions
- through the mafia of laws
- through business for the rich and the over-rich
- by creating a debt system
- through greater poverty
- by reducing rent - income from rents, capital investments, real estate and more
- Through government policies
- By enforcing the laws / example of the European Commission and the European Union
- By creating corruption practices at state institutions - NRA, police
- By creating a mafia in all state institutions
- By creating a mafia in the judiciary - a court, a prosecutor's office,
- Through wars
- By lacking and limiting conversion opportunities
- By making salaries and creating a minimum wage system for 99% of the population
- By creating a poverty group and a group of the over-rich
- Through the tax system - increase in taxes
- By setting a minimum wage and its dependence on GDP and other indicators.
- By supporting foreign direct investment to launder money in the country concerned, by minimizing income compared to developed countries
- By providing a median income that ensures minimal human existence without creating other conversion opportunities

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- Through the mafia of government, economic union, countries
- By generating crises - economic, financial, monetary, demographic, cultural and more.
- By generating refugee crises
- Through crises in social systems
- By mafiaing the judiciary
- By imposing corrupt practices in the state, local government, laws, public procurement,

The sole purpose is the profit and enslavement of peoples, states, governments, the creation of monopolies.
Participating countries - banks, financial institutions, companies - oil, resource, steel, oil, food, medicine, fuels.
Finance and money determine politics, wars, peace.

The goal: neoliberalism and globalization

Control of 99.9% of the population by governments - not only through finances, but also by the cultivation of loyal government and state subjects - from universities, world institutions, clubs, lodges, foundations, and then or become presidents, prime ministers, ministers, heads and important departments.

Robbing 99.9% of the population

Plunder of 99.9% of income, savings - through high taxes, interest rates, increased food prices, increased prices of services, increased prices of consumables, increased interest on credit cards, on fast loans,

Control of security services and compromise management.

Whole country control

Through debt securities control of governments, countries.

Money control, their circulation, movement, direction, direction.

Policy control and policies implemented

Press control

Policy control

Control of Masonic lodges

The meaning and purpose of war, military conflict, aggression - profit.

Control and prevention of technology introduction.

Controlling and preventing the production of free energy technologies for use by all people and peoples.

Control of patents that contribute to the development of civilization, not to see the white light, to be forgotten, not to use.

Control and eradication of scientists who have created innovative solutions for the benefit of humanity in science, technology, and healing.

Control and prevention of the production of developments for the treatment of deadly diseases.

Importing and exporting corruption in a country to destabilize it creates inequality in society.

Imports of terrorism, which creates fear, instability and corresponding inequality.

Export and import of mafia principles in one country.

Creating a debt economy, a debt spiral for 99% of the population, controlling money, controlling money transfers, making money payments, controlling credit, controlling money, controlling countries, societies, nations, governments.

Mastery of the masses, peoples, individuals through racketeering, coercion, orders, use of institutions at state and other levels for racketeering, coercion, extortion, use of prosecutor's office for racketeering, coercion of extortion. .

Personal control, with debit, credit cards, mobile phones, mobile applications - continuous control.

Control of civil society through foundations - NGOs aiming at changing public opinion, financing them for the purpose of controlling and managing society.

Ownership of all the resources of the earth, oil, gold, silver, uranium and their income.

Disease population management.

Management of the population through environmental pollution

Technology management, when to bring one technology to a realization, why not, hold on to another, disappear.

Private repositories of vast wealth.

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Crisis Generation - Any, economic, monetary, social, refugee, conflict, war political crises. The financial crisis arises most rapidly, the currency crisis emerges instantly, followed by economic crises, Part of the financial crisis and one of which is the currency crisis. A financial crisis ensues. There are always economic crises.

A global currency controlled by members of the Financial Banking Technology Mafia Materialism ..

Creating a debt spiral, the responsibilities of individual citizens, families, communities,

End-of-Life Consumption Control PampI Representatives of the FBIHM Materialism

Resource control

Money control

Production control

Schemes for generating crises in neoliberalism and globalization to increase inequality in one people, nation, community, unions, peoples,:

- Calling wars - they lead to deep inequalities. Calling for military conflicts
- Calling military intervention in a foreign country that creates chaos and inequality.
- Import and export of corruption, mafia in all institutions in one country,
- Withdrawal of money from circulation creates immediate economic crises. They, in turn, cause enormous damage to entire countries. It receives loans accordingly.
- Causing a refugee crisis - causes - creates economic, social, demographic, social, political crises.
- Causing the Financial Crisis, Causing the Currency Crisis, Causing the Economic Crisis, - Causing the Political Crisis - Not Last Last
- Increasing the deficit - for the purpose of subordination
- World wars are becoming redundant because of the danger of nuclear exchange, so terrorism, Islamization will be used.
- Managing the population through fears that create stress. Fostering fear among the population.
- Creating an antipode - through fear, manipulation, Creating an intrigue machine
- Creating a machine for seeming occasions - for wars, conflicts, aggressions, sabotages,
- Exciting inflation and deflation afterwards
- Creating an antipode - the ultimate goal of the Cold War battle - is generating huge profits, huge cash flows,
- No mastery of resources, control of resources, management of resources for personal purposes only.
- The machine of intrigues and compromises and the creation of false occasions.
- Generate, fund and combat terrorism.

10. MONEY LAUNDERING, PROFITS, MAKING OF PEOPLES AND STATES through the so-called foreign investment in globalization, liberalism and neoliberalism of THE DEEP MAFIA

Inequality between the income of the workers on both sides - the investor's country and the country where the investment is made.

1 / . Green investment means the following

The Western company registers a company in Bulgaria under Bulgarian law.

The same company under the laws of the state and as an investor or receive with preferences for purchase of land, construction of the state infrastructure, water supply and sewerage, communications, electricity supply and supply of electricity, construction of the state of the respective electricity network for high voltages, communications to transport corridors and more. The parent company registers credit lines for the construction of the respective buildings, equipment, import of equipment and the purchase of equipment. All this - equipment that is obvious company development is accounted for in greater amounts, the companies that build the buildings and premises are carried out by close to the parent company, which account for construction, design and others at higher prices.

Some of these larger sums go back to the parent company.

Realistically for credit lines of 100 units, the real value of these investments is about 30 - 35 units. The rest are amounts that are laundered throughout this process. In addition, the daughter company owes to the parent company on the basis of credit lines and high interest rates.

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Even after production is organized, if the cost of a product is, for example, 100 units, then the finished product is exported to a parent company at a price of 100,001 units.

The taxes are actually paid for 0.001 units. The real profit is made out. Production is fully exported 100 percent. Cost is low here - wages are low and low.

Here, too, wages are between 20 to 30-35% of the real wages in the Western countries.

The first option - even the company - the mother receives a land grant.

The second option - donation - lands.

2 /. In construction - the first scheme. A company is registered. The company receives loans from foreign companies. The money of these companies is not checked for origin of money laundering and others. Credit lines are registered with the relevant government institutions in Bulgaria. Construction is under construction which costs 35% of 100 units in real terms. Here, too, wages are between 20 to 30-35% of the real wages in the Western countries.

3 /. Under Construction - Second Scheme Scheme - Company buys property in the center of Sofia. Receives a loan from a bank with foreign capital. Real Credit - The money is given by companies close to the owners of the bank, which are foreign companies. Money is actually laundered through the bank. All income goes back to the creditors through the bank. Here, too, wages are between 20 to 30-35% of the real wages in the Western countries.

4 /. In Construction - Third Scheme Building Company Stores. The land and the stores and chains are owned by the parent company of the parent company, which have received 100 units of credit. Here, too, wages are between 20 to 30-35% of the real wages in the Western countries.

5 /. Manufacturing companies. The parent company registers a company for the purchase of the respective real estate, construction of the respective construction sites, equips the equipment of the parent company.

The cash for all these expenses is given by the parent company as credit lines - the loans to the firm by the daughter. Interest rates are freely negotiated. Typically, these interest rates are higher than market rates. Borrowings can also be provided by a bank in the territory of the country concerned, as guaranteed by the parent company. In reality, the entire investment returns repeatedly to the parent company of the subsidiary. The products or services produced are actually exported to the parent company at prices close to the cost of the products. No profit is made in the country where the daughter company is registered. Profits are made by the parent company or its branches abroad. Here, too, wages are between 20 and 30-35% of real wages in Western countries.

6 /. Banking services - financial services.

7 /. Property business

8 /. Outsourcing services.

9 /. Company producing petroleum products.

10 /. EXPORTING THE INCOME OF A COUNTRY AS A METHOD OF DIVISION, INCREASING INEQUALITIES IN THE CONSIDERED COUNTRIES WITH THE WESTERN STATES

10.1 /. from Retail chains.

90 - 98% of the products sold are imported from abroad - given on credit with appropriate interest and penalties for delay, for the corresponding term. Prices are made - higher prices are given on consignment

Debt is immediate. The money from the companies' turnover is deposited on a vault in the evening every night in a vault of a banking institution - mostly foreign. The next morning, the next day, the money is posted to a correspondent bank account at a bank, which corresponds to a foreign bank's account from a foreign bank. Realistically, in this correspondent bank account, the party is dumping money into our accounts by our parent company abroad. So no taxes are paid in the state in this case Bulgaria. Turnover per month of drainage of income from Bulgaria is on average between EUR 5-7 billion, non-taxable. This is evidenced by the profits that register chains from grocery stores, consumer goods.

10.2 /. For services or mobile products or services.

The actual payment of these services, if the aim is to use a 10% profit tax in Bulgaria, can be made in the country itself. However, the real situation is this: the money paid for online services is transferred to bank accounts in branches of banks that are not controlled by the Central Bank as they are branches

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10.3./ For banking services. Money laundering, trading, This is done mainly through branches of banks that are not actually controlled by the central bank and are not subject to banking supervision. These branches are by all legal provisions for branches of banks whose headquarters are in another country of a European country. These banks are controlled through banking supervision in the countries where they are registered, but not in the country where they have only branches. The payments in these branches are made mainly by foreign companies on bank accounts, which are correspondent bank accounts of the parent banks or banks abroad, and with the very authentication of these bank accounts, the money is already in the corresponding correspondent bank accounts abroad. No taxes are actually paid on this money. All these schemes are evidenced by the analysis of more than 500 production, commercial, companies, companies from the product sales chains, with real turnover of 400 - 800 million euros, making a profit of 1-2 million euros, which is not really consistent on

THIS IS A CONCLUSION -

Such foreign investment should not be reported in the Gross Domestic Product because it produces misleading results that do not reflect reality. In reality, such foreign investment should be accounted for only in terms of the employed workforce and the corresponding volume of remuneration. This alone must be taken into account in the Gross Domestic Product of the country concerned.

11. GOVERNING Inequality through the Creation of the Debt Spiral and Its Governance and Control in Globalization and Neoliberalism of THE DEEP MAFIA

Debt can be managed, controlled by division.

Reducing mortgage funds, support systems for small and medium-sized businesses, supporting their businesses. Quantitative eases go to the businesses of the rich. Public procurement is managed only and solely by the firms of the rich, the poor and the medium-sized companies are driven by tenders, tenders, and public procurement. Public contracts are awarded to specific large companies so that only they satisfy the conditions and requirements for participation in the respective auction, competition or public procurement. Banks only finance and support the businesses of the rich. European funding goes to the rich companies. Fast Credit Companies. The debt industry is part of the means of creating, managing, controlling the division of society.

The financial industry is a vehicle for this debt industry. The financial industry is providing fast loans with high and huge interest rates. The emergence of fast loan companies, where money laundering, uncontrolled money laundering is just the rich. The rich invest in products, industries, business services for the poor. They practically deepen and accelerate division and inequality. Extended loans for the purchase of cars, furniture, vacations, real estate. Bridge Loans Fast loans to cover heating and food bills. Debt - its increase practically accelerates inequality and division in society. 93% of Bulgarian property is privately owned. By dividing and increasing inequality - virtually poverty causes this property to be reduced as people have to sell their property in order to survive in order to make ends meet. Continuous tax increase, food prices, services, utilities. Debt trading, increasing debt, financial institutions trading our debt. Quantitative eases in the US 2008 actually go to financial institutions instead of going to citizens.

Instead, they should be spent on services, appliances, vacations, refrigerators, TVs, cars. Instead, these quantitative easements have exacerbated and increased inequality and division.

The plan was more debt. Throwing money in a crisis actually creates more inequality and division of society. Calculating Poverty - Getting Out of Debt - Increasing Debt. All measures taken by governments to ensure that people have more debt. Currently, household debt in the UK is around £ 395 billion.

12. NEOLIBERALISM AND GLOBALIZATION - THE ENVIRONMENTAL MAKING BETWEEN STATES through the International Monetary Fund and the World Bank, World Trade Organization toolkit of THE DEEP MAFIA

The policies of the IMF and the World Bank - the indebtedness of entire nations, peoples of countries, with a view to long increasing the divide of inequality, buying - privatization of state-owned enterprises, funds, resources, entire economic sectors. Inequality between countries.

Creation of crises and, at the same time, the IMF and the World Bank offering to help countries overcome these crises. Creating crises in Latin America.

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The IMF offers assistance to address these crises. The IMF is failing to deal with these crises. This is deliberately done. The ultimate goal is to create a debt spiral of these countries to the IMF and the World Bank.

The result of these impacts - deepening disparities, accelerating the lagging behind of these countries from other countries - increasing inequalities between countries.

When do these crises occur in Latin America, for example. When the interests of the United States are threatened in those regions that are very rich in natural resources.

Example The US is losing its lead revenue in Bolivia after nationalization of lead mines. The result - the United States is looking for an option to overthrow the government. 1952 General Barrientos wins the election. Steps - The military dictatorship opens Bolivia's doors to foreign capital wide open.

The IMF's stabilization strategies include the following steps:

Free currency exchange rate (introduction of special customs tariffs).

Freezing wages - leading to widespread unemployment.

Lack of social programs.

Bolivia has been brought down.

The same thing happened in 1960 in Uruguay. There is an increasing deficit in the state budget. The national and 88 foreign banks, created in 1949 - 1959, contribute to the instability of Uruguay. 1954 Uruguay exports gold to the United States. For \$ 16.5 million. The country is plagued by misery. Difficult supply of the population with basic goods and services.

The IMF also prohibits Uruguay from entering into bilateral trade treaties with foreign countries it cannot control. However, such bilateral treaties lead to increased trade and stabilization of economies., Exports of goods, resources. The IMF takes control of all Uruguay's trade and financial operations. The IMF also puts Montevideo's National Bank under control. 1968 The IMF orders the Uruguayan National Bank to reduce its public sector loans and increase foreign loans. which makes them more dependent on foreign loans. As a result, inflation jumped tenfold between 1966 and 1972. \$ 350 billion is being spent outside the country. Uruguay's foreign debt increased by 5.3 billion pesos in 1967. up to 14.7 billion pesos in 1970. Speculation and the black market are growing. Crime and inequality are increasing.

1956 causes the crisis in Argentina. The agreement with the IMF reduces the stock of foreign currency, foreign trade, prices increase, the balance of payments is undermined, the state is obliged to submit complete information to the IMF which information is really relevant for national security and national defense. The state allows foreign capital to flow. The benefits received from the fund are much less than promised. For the period 1958 to 1970, the Argentine peso was 13 devalued. The standard of living has fallen sharply, the population is massively impoverished, and the state regulation is strengthening.

In the late 1950s, Brazil experienced hyperinflation, based on low coffee buying prices. , wages fall 4 times, In fact, national resources are acquired by foreign companies.

Brazil seeks the assistance of IMF. The measures are to reduce the wage quotas for employees in the budgetary sector from 37% to 27%. , 300,000 personnel from state-owned enterprises have been laid off. this is 20%. The difference between rich and poor is deepening. The total poverty of the population is increasing.

1968 Peru co-ordinates with the IMF the creation of 450 foreign companies. These companies are from Japan, Germany, the United States Debts to foreign countries increase enormously. the country is insolvent. In 1970, representatives of foreign companies who violated the laws of the state were sued in Peru. Partial nationalization is taking place. In 1972. the state investments are 39%, in 1973 - 42%, in 1974 - 43%.

There is a strong link between strong economic groups and foreign capital, leading to economic de-stabilization. This applies to Brazil, Argentina, Chile ..

The IMF aims for liberalization for foreign capital, no stabilization on the national market. The goal is foreign companies entering the countries, exporting resources, goods, national wealth, without engaging in the development of the local economy, markets, consumption. Inequality grows dramatically, discontent grows in strikes and riots, poverty increases. Crime is increasing,

In Jamaica, after the nationalization of the bauxite industry, which is a major item of income in the national budget, economic growth began to decline, sovereign debt increased from 1973 to 1980 from \$ 501 million to \$ 1.595 billion in 1992. and in 1992. it's already \$ 2 billion. Jamaica is seeking the assistance of the IMF, which promises \$ 240 million over a 3-year period, and returns to foreign investors and related strata instead of returning to productions instead of returning to

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productions. More than \$ 300 million is actually flowing. As a result, consumer prices are rising, poverty is rising, oil, electricity and water prices are rising. , unemployment increases dramatically, IMF is not really interested in any social activities, New IMF contract - results in freezing of wages, creating favorable conditions for foreign capital inflow, restricting the use of currency, 1982. Jamaica's unemployment reaches 26%. The militarization of the country with the help of the USA began in 1982. Jamaica becomes the first US aid to the Grenada aggression.

Regulating the economies of Latin American countries through IMF accelerates and increases their independence. In the IRF system, it creates speculation and crime.

Depreciation of the national currency, rising debt, accelerated inflation, reducing stability, creating chaos, constantly creating conflicts, exporting capital, absorbing and acquiring the resources of the countries of nothing, 1988 alone exported capital \$ 420 billion from Latin America.

The IMF does not change its strategy and approach even after an increase in liabilities, which in reality leads to an inability to repay its financial obligations, reduces investment, which in turn increases volatility and accelerates the debt spiral.

The main tool the IMF advises on deficit management is the currency devaluation, which in turn accelerates the debt spiral. This is proven for Brazil in 1986, in Mexico for 1986, Argentina - 1986-1988.

It also leads to a decrease in production. For Chile it is 15: for the period 1974-1975, for Venezuela it is 8% for 1989, in Peru - it is 6% for 1990.

The devaluation leads to an incredible increase in inflation, which accelerates the debt spiral. All this leads to hyperinflation. For Argentina, inflation has reached 4000% in the 1980s. 40% of the population is impoverished sharply and quickly. The other instrument that the IMF is destroying countries is privatization. The purpose of the IRF and the representatives of the FBIHM - Materialism is to buy the main sectoral businesses at a price from nearby living rooms.

This is all included in the so-called shock therapy. The banking reforms that the IMF aims and prepares for the ultimate purpose are to privatize the banks and from there the assets, the firms - of the main industries, the foreign trade companies, the main enterprises for the production of resources, goods,

13. NEOLIBERALISM OF HAYEK AND FRIEDMAN AND CRITICISM TO IT BY PROF. DR. MOMCHIL DOBREV

Neoliberalism arose in the 20s and 30s of the 20th century,

The theoretical foundations of neo-liberalism date from classical liberalism of the 19th century.

The economic system is built on the basis of market economy, which is regulated by free competition.

Liberal classics reject the possibility of state intervention.

Neoliberalism recognizes the interference of the state in economic life, but only when the state maintains and works for free competition.

Neoliberalism is the antithesis of the Keynesian economic system - which justifies the need for state intervention in the country's economic life. This theory became dominant in the 30s and 40s after Black Friday, with economic crises in the 70s showing that the state was a weak regulator of economic life.

After World War II, neo-liberalism began to play an important role in Western European countries, and especially in England, / London School /, USA / Chicago School /, Germany / Freiburg School /, France, Italy and Belgium. This is required by the accelerated development of the countries sought after the Second World War.

In the early 1970s, neoliberalism boomed in economic thought. This is after the awarding of Nobel Prizes by economist Friedrich von Hayek and Milton Friedman. This is based on accelerated economic growth. It comes after the state's excessive interference in economic life has been abolished, which is accompanied by all the dangers to freedom that result from it.

Neo-liberals believe that the state is incapable of securing the well-being of all members of society and this necessitates a restriction of its powers.

Hayek and Friedman believe that proportional rather than progressive taxation is a central feature of neoliberalism.

In financial policy, neoliberals maintain the principle of a balanced budget. In the area of monetary policy, the state should be deprived of its monopoly on issuing money.

In the area of social policy, freedom, the enforcement of antitrust laws and consumer protection measures, free initiative, guaranteeing fundamental free citizens should be restricted to a minimum.

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The main elements are - priority of private property, low taxes, restrictive social policy, stable money supply, restriction of state intervention in the economy and anti-regulatoryism.

London School

This school is called "often and neo-Austrian" since the founder of the London School was Friedrich August von Hayek in 1899, Carl Popper and Linnell Robins.

The concept is for economic development as a spontaneous process, the perception of the economic freedom of individuals and the exclusion of the possibility of state intervention.

According to Hayek, the "spontaneous order" in a market economy is evolutionarily created as an unconscious result of the conscious free actions of individuals,.

People are driven by personal incentives to achieve mutual benefit, although no one is guided by thoughts of the good of the community.

According to Hayek, there should be no state intervention in the economy, no protectionist policy,

The state should exercise only administrative functions, with the sole purpose of not infringing on the freedom of individuals, ie. not to violate the interests of capital and labor.

Contradiction. The interests of capital and labor are opposite.

The principles of free competition do not alter the law of supply and demand.

Both supply and demand are managed ie. there is no independence of this law.

Chicago School.

In the 1940s, the neoclassicism trend emerged in the United States as one of the currents of neoliberalism. The founder of neoliberalism in the United States is Milton Friedman, and representatives are Edward Chamberlain, Bevjamin Anderson, Maurice Copeland.

The real Keynesian paradigm collapsed in the 1970s,

The ideas of the Austrian School are supported by Ludwig von Mises, Murray Rothbard, Israel Krisner.

Monetarism is the most prominent manifestation of neoliberalism / neo-conservatism / gained influence in the late 1970s and 1980s in the United States. They show the bankruptcy of the Keynesian model, according to which the active intervention of the state is crucial for the stability of the economy.

They believe that there are internal forces for self-regulation of the economy. They argue that there were stabilizing factors governing the economic equilibrium, underlining the fundamental importance of the monetary system in the economic process. According to the monetarists, the high rates of monetary circulation increase caused by the wrong monetary policy were the cause of inflation, cyclical unemployment, and crises in the monetary balance.

Freiburg School

The founder of neoliberalism in Germany is Walter Aiken (1891-1950) - professor of political economy. His supporters are L. Erhard, A. Müller-Armak, V. Röpke, A. Rostov, F. Ben, H. Trossman-Derton. They create some theories, the most famous of which is "social market economy theory".

The economic basis of this economy is the free market based on free competition, which is provided by the state through its legislative powers. They protect free competition. State interventionism in the United States by President Franklin Delano Roosevelt under the so-called "New Deal" is the key to overcoming the Great Depression from 1929 to 1933.

This new course is the real Keynesian model of business functioning. This is, in reality, a type of government - "state - olipopolistic mafia capitalism".

Neo-liberalism marked its heyday in the 1960s, after economic institutions from London and Chicago identified the institutions critical of the Keynesian model. This is the so-called Chicago School. In reality, this school realizes the ideologies of the financial bank resource technological mafia materialism of Prof. Momchil Dobrev. His representatives are M. Friedman, F. White, J. Stigler and others.

On the Keynesian model of a set of regulatory measures implemented by the state to stimulate economic activity and business processes, the Chicago School opposes the so-called "clean" market mechanism. They link economic crises with monetary and credit disruptions.

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According to them, the most important tool for the state's impact on the economy is the amount of money.

Actually, based on the conclusions of the Financial Banking Technology Mafiosiren Materialism Prof. Momchil Dobrev, it is evident that in a conscious management of the money supply, crises are created - monetary, economic, financial. Currency crises in which the national currency's exchange rate against the dollar jumps incredibly and really as a result of the depreciation of the national currency.

Simply the scheme of varying the size of the currency - the presence of currency, the retention of currency, the restriction of access to the currency - causes the devaluation of the national currency. Real neo-liberalism, along with neo-conservatism in the 1970s, came to power in the United States through President Ronald Reagan and in the United Kingdom through Prime Minister Margaret Thatcher.

At one point neo-conservatism gives way to neoliberalism. On the basis of globalization, the classic Friedrich von Hayek, a British economist and sociologist of Austrian descent, has been introduced into neoliberalism as the basis of the representatives of the financially resourceful technological mafia materialism of Prof. Momchil Dobrev in neoliberalism.

In reality, neither "Reaganomics" nor "Thatcherism" forms a neoliberal model of government. In reality, US and UK neoliberalism has emerged as an "export model" implemented through the "Washington Consensus".

The neoliberal model is proving to be a new model for the reborn nomenclature elite - a mechanism for quickly and effectively solving the problem of transferring property from state to private.

In this way, the real representatives of the Finanosian bank resource technological mafia materialism of Prof. Momchil Dobrev from the West are aiming for the real economic ruin of the already former adversary - the former socialist countries, with the aim of actually de-colonizing the resources in these countries of the East by these representatives.

In this way Bulgaria was also put into the framework of "neoliberalism".

In reality, the ideology of neoliberalism places at the center of its ideology the "economic man" - calculating, predicting, rationally choosing and knowing his economic interest. On the basis of this view of "economic person" is formed the need for complete freedom of action of this "economic man". In their view, this is a real condition for human progress.

In reality, these individuals associate the freedom of action of an "economic man" with the unrestricted mechanisms of market game.

In reality, this is absolutism.

Market game is really the only condition for development. "There's nothing to sell and anything can be bought.

The question depends on whether there is a search. In reality, the "market game" transcends and replaces the totality of all other human values. Any attempt to seek a unifying human society with ethics and morality is viewed by neo-liberal theorists as a "path to slavery" - according to Friedrich von Hayek.

This paradigm really overturns the whole essence of human society and human essence. In reality, the question of human morality is raised on a market basis - ie. "Anything that is inefficient in the marketplace and does not maximize profit is timeless. According to this ideology, the human and human meter are the sole marketplace.

If the market does not accept an individual, that is, he does not make maximum profit, then this person is not entitled to exist. This makes sense of the whole essence of human society.

ie morality and values are depreciated as anything that has value and value and only sells it. ie The law of supply and demand is really amoral. Because only this is sought and offered which brings money - ie. morality is depreciated. Moral ethical, legal norms are devalued.

ie everything is corrupt.

In our view, however, what is moral and moral is socially just.

This is excluded in neoliberalism - morality, moral norms, legal norms are excluded.

Not everything can be sold, not everything can be offered at any price.

In reality, neo-liberalism was aimed at restricting freedom.

In reality, freedom is associated with being able to offer and seek everything at a certain price. ie this means that morality is offered at a fixed price.

Morality, ethical rules cannot and should not be traded.

Going real with market freedom leads to real slavery of man and everything moral, ethical,

In neoliberalism, it is mainly economic and commercial freedom. It makes growth, development,

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Neoliberalism is an ideology and a political agenda and system that outstrips free markets. Every battle against neoliberalism is seen as a battle against free markets.

But who owns the "free markets" and are they "free"?

Markets are not free at all since they are dominated by huge companies that impose their marketing and branding strategies, impose their prices, increase their business, conquer more and more territories and leave no free territory for competition.

There is really no competition.

For example, is it competition in Bulgaria - like German supermarket chains and superstores - sells products manufactured in Bulgaria at 4 times higher prices than those sold by these Bulgarian producers - with a foreign owner in foreign markets - Angolan and German. Is this a limited competition?

There is really no access to markets, no real competition, there are imposition of marketing, branding strategies, product promotion strategies. , prices, goods, services.

Actually who owns the market, he also owns the income of the population.

There is a real dominance of certain companies in certain markets. Neoliberalism really has nothing to do with free markets. All these are words and words to manipulate.

Is there is a conduct of the public system in the name and for the benefit of the market;

There is a real, forced, undemocratic and unequal reorganization of the foundations of a society.

What is achieved:

- Intensification and extensification
- Enhancing, accelerating, differentiating differences
- Strengthening, accelerating, segregating inequalities
- Strengthening, accelerating the separation of the debt spiral and impoverishment
- Reinforce, accelerate division

Not fair distribution of public goods.

At the core are global corporations that manage, create, control, market and price within it with the ultimate goal of maximizing profits, draining all the population.

Neoliberalism is a deliberate deliberate act to subvert the moral ethical rules of law in order to cause a loss of judgment against the law.

According to neoliberalism, human beings are a calculator of profits and losses.

Moral ethical norms are ignored and the goal is to weaken the welfare state and any commitment of the state to the people.

Neoliberalism is a method of rearranging human society. Neoliberalism makes every person think of themselves as the owner of their knowledge and initiative, talents, to compete and to constantly adapt. Relations between people are no longer seen as competition alone. Neoliberalism regards competition as the only legitimate organizational principle of human society and human activity.

The market is the sole appraiser of the qualities of man, his worth and the sole guardian of human freedom. This system of evaluating the quality of each person in terms of price and value actually produces a small part - a caste of winners and a huge army of losers only.

Hayek believes that it solves the problem of modernity, the problem of operational knowledge. According to Hayek, the market legitimizes the trade in goods and services with precisely defined prices and value for the qualities of the human personality, but the market only reveals the truth.

The reverence for the free market causes the values of the human being and the human personality, which have no price and cannot be sold, to be erased.

This is a real creation of a new world - a world governed by the rich only for their benefit and profit.

According to Hayek, the market can be considered a kind of consciousness.

While Adam Smith thinks that the market can only be justified in the light of individual values, the virtues of the human personality, he is real concerned that when society rests and develops solely on self-interest, it will not be human society.

Hayek is considered the forerunner of neoliberalism, which reduces everything to a market and economy, to goods and services of prices and values. Hayek considers the price system on the market as reason and the only reason that is effective,

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logical, useful to society. Hayek structures the whole reality on the model of economic competition and the supply and sale of goods and services only at a certain value and price.

But to transform human values as goods and services at a certain price, it embodies the real human essence and is only the prerogative of the rich and the oligarchy which aims only at profit regardless of the value of human life. Hayek considers and believes that every human activity is conscious and only then valuable when it has economic value and cost. Human activities can be brought to the basic concept of wealth, value, price, exchange, cost and above all price. Prices are a means of effectively allocating scarce resources, considerations, needs, and benefits.

Human activities and qualities must be cost and value. Prices are determined by supply and demand. For a market to function well, it must be free and competitive.

Civil society, human values, moral values, ethical values of man, free institutions freedom of conscience, honor, dignity, religion, the press find no place in Hayek's thinking. According to Hayek, only the market provides the only protection of society against totalitarianism. In order to prevent totalitarianism, the state must only guarantee market freedom. These are just thoughts. While in liberalism the state must leave the traders of peace, in neoliberalism the state must be active in organizing free markets. It is the state that must constantly maintain market freedom.

Everything should be based on economic values and analysis. On the other hand, the state should leave sufficient autonomy on the market, so as not to disturb the natural functioning of the markets.

Therefore, ideally, the state provides conditions - a neutral, independent, fixed, universal legal framework in which market forces to act spontaneously arise.

The price system is the one that manages and manages the market of everything.

According to Hayek, the free market left on its own mechanisms, with its price system, acts as a reason. I.e. the market calculates what individuals cannot realize. The market values people with their prices and values.

I.e. according to Hayek, the market is a means of knowing, Such a market is not a human invention, and it can be manipulated like anything else.

Hayek does not even consider the possibilities of market manipulation and its prices.

He doesn't even look at it, he doesn't even mention it.

This is not accidental. These are the means of monopolies, of the originality, which uses manipulation to control, create, control the market and its prices.

The sole public purpose is to maintain the market itself.

Again, this is for the sole benefit of monopolies and oligarchy.

The market is the only legitimate form of knowledge. At the individual level, our values are only personal, they are just an opinion that does not need to be accepted.

Values that have no value and price are not respected.

It is no coincidence that Ronald Reagan and Margaret Thatcher are the proponents of Hayek's neo-liberalism; this proved their support for the monopolies and the oligarchy that governs the states, with the ultimate goal of governing, creating, marketing, setting rules, pricing values and winning.

Thatcher praised Hayek and promised to unite his free-market philosophy with the revival of Victorian values: family, community, hard work. But I really forget that. Neoliberalism is really at the heart of any crisis, especially the crisis of 2007-2008. Profits and transfers of money into offshore accounts and zones.

Real neoliberalism is at the root and cause of the collapse of public health, education, child poverty, ecosystem collapse,

Inequality is a virtue, the market guarantees that every person receives what he or she deserves, depending on its price and value.

For neoliberalism, competition is the most important characteristic of human relationships.

Real neoliberalism defines citizens as consumers whose choice is determined by buying and selling. It is the market that rewards human quality and punishes its inefficiency. According to Hayek, the market provides benefits that have accrued by accident not going as planned. The real restriction of competition is imprisonment. Taxes and regulations should be minimized. Public services must be privatized. According to neoliberalism, collective agreements and the actions of trade unions distort the market. The market is determined by a hierarchy of winners and losers.

Inequality is a generator of wealth and a reward for utility.

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It is the market that guarantees and provides everyone with what they deserve.

On the one hand, the poor blame themselves and, according to neoliberalism, they must blame themselves for not being successful, not being effective, not being useful.

Being unemployed means that the person is not enterprising, useless, has no real value and cost to look for.

In a world governed only by competition and the market, those who are unsuccessful must look for the blame alone, and therefore they are the losers.

The term neoliberalism occurs in 1938. at a meeting in Paris, attended by two of its representatives Ludwig von Mises and Friedrich Hayek.

In *The Road to Slavery*, published in 1944. Hayek argues that "governmental planning by crushing individualism will inevitably lead to totalitarian control. This is similar in Mises' book *Bureaucracy*.

Most of all, the titles of these books attract the attention of rich people who are beginning to finance these theses. Hayek began to establish a transatlantic network of academics, businessmen, journalists and wealthy business activists.

While Hayek believes that governments must regulate competition in order to prevent monopolies from forming, he is inferior to Milton Friedman, believing that monopoly power should be seen as a remuneration for efficiency.

Hayek introduces the quota theory of spontaneous order in the market.

Ludwig von Mises and Friedrich von Hayek did not cease to be critical of the mainstream economy, even between the 1930s and 1970s. The economic crisis of the early 1970s gave rise to a new look at monetary theory and the theory of the economic business cycle. Therefore, they are looking for solutions that respond to unexplained processes that include high inflation and low employment.

The turning point came in 1974 when Friedrich von Hayek was awarded the Nobel Prize in Economics with his work on monetary theory and the theory of the economic business cycle.

Hayek's analysis begins with the market. For Hayek, the market is an institution of spontaneous public order. Free spontaneous markets and free will are interconnected and conditioned. According to Hayek, "freedom is a situation in which individuals are not dependent on the arbitrariness of others. 1948

For Hayek, information and knowledge play an important role, they are the main drivers of market processes. There is no perfect information available to match the expectation with reality. According to Hayek, personalities adapt to the market and improve conditions for themselves by improving the knowledge and information available through the market itself.

Regulation must only be done through the market itself and the market itself.

Hayek develops a theory of equilibrium in the market of Leon Vapras, who assumes that it is aesthetics with perfect knowledge of market players.

According to Hayek, balance is a dynamic category due to incomplete awareness.

But this lack of awareness is managed and controlled by monopolies and the oligarchy, which does not allow full market awareness.

It is the Mafia that controls the market's distortion. It makes awareness.

The discrepancy between search and supply and because of incomplete information and incomplete market information.

The Mafia manages the flow of information. The Mafia owns the information, there is no perfect information, they hide the information, they restrict access to information, they restrict information.

According to representatives of the Austrian School, money is what causes supply and demand imbalances and is a generator of cyclical fluctuations.

Controlling the amount of money supply can avoid cyclicity in crises.

Hayek, however, emphasizes more on the secondary effect of the monetary policy of the government, namely the discrepancy between the structure of production and the inclinations for savings in society.

The Stagflation Depression of 1972 Hayek explains with a disturbance of the dynamic equilibrium in the structure of production.

Changes in the supply of money by the central bank have a real impact on the market economy.

Money is the one that causes a mismatch between the search and the marketing.

According to Prof. Dr. Momitchl Dobrev, the availability of free money from profits from non-productive activities - trade services and others generate crises.

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Neo-liberalism through globalization guarantees the management of the market by monopolies and oligarchy.

The cyclical destabilization, which is the result of the monetary policy of central authorities, influences the change in the structure of production, which is incompatible with the specific norm of saving in society. The change in the money supply by each central bank has an impact on the structure of production, trade, consumption, and savings. Money is the one that causes a mismatch between supply and demand in the economy. Wrong information, marketing of wrong information.

The creation of capital goods is achieved.

The market calculates all unprofitable productions through deflation.

Secondary deflation leads to a loss of confidence.

Neoliberalism leads to a setback on social and economic benefits.

Neoliberalism puts at the top of society's existence - individual freedoms that do not obey any rules.

This is completely wrong because order in a social society is provided by ethical, moral, legal norms.

It is no coincidence that 5th century BC, Hammurabi introduced moral, ethical and legal norms into the laws that govern a society.

According to another neo-liberal representative, Milton Friedman, inflation was a monetary phenomenon. These words rest on the faith of the power of the central banks for more than 30 years.

In reality, Milton Friedman gives central banks the power to govern societies. - this proves that Milton Friedman really protects the representatives of Prof. Momchil Dobrev's Financial Resource Technology Mafia Materialism whose sole purpose is huge profits, the enslavement of entire nations and peoples to work for them, a real slavery.

According to Milton Friedman, the money supply of money by central banks determines the price of money. However, if the bankers act properly there will be no inflation or deflation and the economy will only grow smoothly.

Actually, the value of money depends on the amount of money put into circulation.

Organizing currency - currency in circulation and access to currency - leads to inflation and devaluation of the currency in question - George Soros systems are examples.

However, money is not a commodity like any other in terms of production value in supply and demand. It is money that measures and measures units of everything.

It is a lie that increasing or decreasing money supply cannot lead to inflation.

Milton Friedman's monetary theory presents the following basic principles:

- The free market is a stable self-regulating system that loses its stability in every state impact
 - The state should not be allowed to produce material assets, regulate employment and prices
 - Floating exchange rates are preferable to fixing, because the fixed rates create a black market and a large amount of transactions are made there
 - In order to stimulate production, it is necessary to maintain a constant low rate of increase in the amount of money in circulation
 - Change in the amount of money in circulation with the main reason for changes in nominal income
 - Unemployment, inflation, stagnation and more are all caused by wrong government policies
 - Government measures aimed at redistributing income through progressive taxation are economically inefficient
 - The government is needed as a means of determining the rules of the game, and is a judge who interprets the established rules and enforces them.
 - Continued inflation is the result of printing too much money
 - Restricting the use of monetary policy to stimulate the economy
 - The implementation of shock therapy - full privatization, free trade and government spending cuts, deregulation
- The quantity of money has no relation to their quality - their purchase value.

Inflation has been a matter of balance between market demand and supply and the expectations of business in government. Economic growth is a kind of perpetuum mobil and self-organizing by itself. As higher expectations of the business lead to more investments that support consumption and increase inflation expectations. Market balloons inflate as final demand begins to fall behind as investment rises. Deflation is the opposite. The inflation spurt, as well as the hyperinflation of the Friedman compound, are made possible when the economy as a whole has no balance between supply and demand.

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Here is the criticism of Prof. Momchil Dobrev that investment is not leading to production and investment in production.

According to Friedman, an increase or decrease in money supply alone cannot trigger inflation.

Prof. Momchil Dobrev's practice and experience and findings and conclusions show exactly the opposite - that managing cash resources, blocking cash, leads to hyperinflation.

After Margaret Thatcher and Ronald Reagan came to power, the introduction of the other components followed as follows:

- Tax relief for the rich, oiling up of unions, deregulation of everything, privatization, outsourcing, and competition for public services.

- Through the policies of the IMF, the World Bank, the Maastricht Treaty and the World Trade Organization, the full range of policies of neo-liberalism is imposed, especially without democratic consent and force on the whole world. in USA.

- Chile is the first country to adopt new "no alternative" policies that promote freedom and choice. The program of neo-liberalism is fully implemented in Chile. However, freedom concerns only the rich, but not the poor.

- Freedom from union and the lack and dismantling of collective bargaining, the signifier of neoliberal liberty.

Freedom means /:

- Reducing pay levels
- No regulation
- Accrual of huge interest rates
- Exotic financial instruments.
- From taxes
- Freedom from distribution of goods
- Financial speculation
- Free movement of capital
- Freedom of money and money laundering

Milton Friedman and Ludwig von Hayek advocate the use, challenge, and recovery of crises. They consider crises as a method of healing and creating new conditions.

Where neo-liberalism may not impose principles and programs and policies, it is compelled by so-called WTO trade agreements by imposing a system of investor-state dispute settlement through offshore arbitration tribunals whereby corporations can coerce countries to repeal social, environmental and other protections and regulations. This is all done to the benefit of international corporations and the international oligarchy. In this way, states are robbed of corporations. In reality, democracy is devoid of face.

The requirement of neoliberalism for the state is to impose universal competition. Actually, all water management utilities are being privatized,

However, according to Prof. Momchil Dobrev, crises are a real system and management of middle-class robbery and 99% of the population of a country.

Inequalities in the distribution of goods and the wrong distribution of goods cause the rich to become richer and the poor to multiply. By privatizing or marketing publicly-traded services that distribute public goods such as electricity, heating, water, trains, healthcare, education, roads, prisons, it allows corporations that privatize them or who receive management concessions to set the prices they want, economically unreasonable and thus pricing - incredibly high somewhere with a 500-800% increase, with corporations actually setting up cash desks to ask for prices that are not actually made. Ie this income is actually unprocessed. This is real non-interest income. Like the interest in the banks, there is an unearned income.

The corporations that have privatized such public services are amassing enormous wealth. There, the profit margins are thousands of percent. This can be seen, for example, in the United Kingdom, India, Russia, and Mexico.

The rich actually manage and control money as another asset. They earn unprocessed income from this asset.

For the last 40 years, there has been a process of shifting the wealth from those who create new products and goods to those rich who only control and manage money and earn a non-working income - the interest on money. Revenue earned is replaced by unearned income.

Bank failure is paid by the state, ie. from the people. Ie profit remains for the business and the rich, and the risk remains for the state - for the people.

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Governments privatize public services, deregulate corporations, regulate citizens, bring down the health care system, pensions, education.

In reality, this is also the case in politics, as large groups of the population are manipulated to manipulate their voting rights.

In reality, there is a kind of totalitarian rule, in which the state forces the people to obey it in whatever pleases the rich.

Through the freedom of movement of capital, goods, people, the conquest of markets, whole countries by multinational companies and corporations, by financial mastodons, becomes real. One model by which capital liberalization is used for product trading is the franchising model of conquering markets, countries, countries of international corporations. In reality, Friedman's book *The Road to Slavery, Bureaucracy, or Capitalism and Freedom* is nothing new, since the interests of the rich to conquer and occupy the world and to gain gains from the new globalized order are clearly and proven.

In reality, these roads are roads to power.

Another form of seizure of public assets is the creation of public - private partnerships between the state and international corporations, even in areas such as defense and weapons development, in the field of security.

Public - private partnerships emerged in the 1980s and especially in the 1990s. In this way, the state or local government assigns tasks to the private sector, which in reality, however, enjoy huge profits, so that, if there are even losses, the state will pay them, exaggerate the costs and values of their investments in infrastructure.

The lack of oversight and control makes the whole process unmanageable, where profits are huge and any information leakage is "commercial confidentiality".

Private companies entering the defense and security sector actually began in January 2001 to take place after the September 11, 2001 event. , under the "war on terror" thesis, such public - private partnerships are created with the ultimate goal of securing huge profits for private corporations paid by the state. The real invasion of foreign countries by these public-private partnerships and the invasion of privacy of citizens provides trillions of dollars in business. This is a business for terrorism - the market for terrorism with the ultimate goal of making huge profits. This displaces and replaces war as a system for providing huge profits. The real result is coercion, lack of democracy, repression, inequality, widespread control and repression. These PPPs actually participate in wars, conquer countries act across borders, actively participate in hostilities, seize resources, drain resources.

In the end, after the 2008 financial crisis, the blame was shifted to change capitalism and financial institutions, and the change in government and blame was transferred to the state, not the real guilty. Finally, after 2008, constitutional and legal changes were introduced that obliged states to change in the name and for the benefit of financial institutions. In addition, laws were adopted to criminalize freedom of assembly and protest to restrict citizens' rights. Such laws were adopted in 2015 in Spain, Canada.

One example in the US is the crackdown on Occupy activists.

The crackdown on protests in Turkey in 2013, the massacre in Mexico in 2014, South Afris 2012.

Real neoliberalism is an ideology that actively promotes the forced, non-democratic and inequitable reorganization of society solely for the benefit of the rich.

There is a real undermining of citizens' social and police rights.

Since 2001, a merger of power, business and security has actually taken place.

In the name of the economic need for the profits of the rich, the democratic rights of citizens are curtailed.

In reality, there is justification for violence and repression in the name of "democracy".

The state is no longer the embodiment of the will of the people, but of corporations, business, the mafia.

The conclusions of Prof. Momchil Dobrev are as follows: Not only monetary policy but also free money received from profit from non-productive activity - and especially from activities in trade, profits from sale of military equipment, profits from non-productive activities - such as trade - the most -more with high rates of profit, profits from speculation, profits from financial activity, profits from trading the liberating huge money supply that is realized in such industries where the profits are huge - at least 300 - 800 percent and one - two years - which is the construction, drugs,

Encouraging monetary policy activity produces good results in the short term but not in the long term.

The basic interest rate is the main source of information for each market entity.

This source of information really distorts the expectations and preferences it gives to the supply and demand.

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CONCLUSIONS

Real neoliberalism is an ideology, a system that creates globalization with the ultimate goal of making profits for international corporations, the oligarchy, the financial representatives of the Financial Banking Resource Technology Mafia Materialism and the DEEP MAFIA.

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